

Study of kinetic parameters and stability constants of [Mn-antibiotics-cefoperazone] complexes vis-a-vis kinetics of electrode reaction

Farid Khan* and Rakhi Agrawal

Electrochemical Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar-470 003, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : faridkhan58@yahoo.com; farid.fk@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : Kinetic parameters and stability constant of complexes of Mn with doxycycline, chlortetracycline, oxytetracycline, tetracycline, monocyline, amoxicillin and chloramphenicol as primary ligands and cefoperazone as secondary ligand have been reported polarographically at $\text{pH} = 7.30 \pm 0.01$, $\mu = 1.0 \text{ M NaClO}_4$ at 25°C . Mn^{2+} formed 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 complexes. The stability constant ($\log \beta$) varied from 1.85 to 9.25 showed that these drugs or in combination with cefoperazone or their metal complexes could be used for Mn toxicity. The values of kinetic parameters viz. transfer coefficient (α), degree of irreversibility (λ) and rate constant (k) confirmed that the electrode processes were quasireversible and the 'transition state' is a function of applied potential. A small variation in potential not only affects the rate but rate constant greatly.

Keywords : Cefoperazone, Mn, antibiotic, kinetics, stability constant.

Introduction

Antibiotics are natural compound produced mostly by plant, microorganism¹. These antibiotics are used against several fungal and bacterial diseases in plants, animals and human beings².

On the other hand, manganese is an important element present in many living organisms, its primary uses in medicines are as germicides and antiseptic. Manganese is also a cofactor in a number of enzymatic reactions like phosphorylation, cholesterol and fatty acids synthesis. Hence the complexes of Mn with antibiotics have great importance³.

Results and discussion

Mn^{2+} gave two electron quasireversible reduction wave at $\text{pH} = 7.30 \pm 0.01$ and $\mu = 1.0 \text{ M NaClO}_4$ at 25°C ⁴. The nature of current-voltage curves for complexes is also quasireversible. The concentration of Mn^{2+} , NaClO_4 and Triton X-100 (as suppressor) in the test solution were 0.5 mM, 1.0 M and 0.001 % respectively. In [Mn-antibiotics-cefoperazone] system, the concentration of antibiotics varied from 0.5 mM to 30.0 mM at 0.025 M and 0.050 M of [cefoperazone] respectively. The $E_{1/2}$ values became more negative with the addition of cefoperazone

to the [Mn-antibiotics] system which showed ternary complex formation of 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 complexes. Gellings⁵ method was used to determine the values of $E_{1/2}^r$ from $E_{1/2}^{qr}$ value by plotting $(E - RT/nF) \log (i_d - i)/i$ vs i for all the complexes. The data and plots of F_{ij} [X, Y] against [X] (where F_{ij} is a Schaap and McMaster⁶ function to evaluate the stability constant β_{ij} , X = doxycycline, Y = cefoperazone and i and j are their stoichiometric numbers respectively) for [Mn-doxycycline-cefoperazone] system were shown in Fig. 1 which is used to determine the values of functions F_{00} , F_{10} , F_{20} and F_{30} and also to calculate the stability constants and the values of these were given in Table 1.

The waves for Mn^{2+} and its complexes were quasireversible as confirmed by kinetic parameters and slopes of current-voltage data. For other systems, the waves were quasireversible also.

The kinetic parameters viz. transfer coefficient (α), degree of irreversibility (λ) and rate constant (k) were determined by Tamamushi and Tanaka methods^{7,8}. The parameter Z , which is a measure of the degree of irreversibility has been calculated by the equation given in the literature⁷.

Fig. 1. Plot of $F_{ij}[X, Y]$ vs $[X]$ for [Mn-doxycycline-cefoperazone] system.

cefoperazone], [Mn-amoxicillin-cefoperazone] and [Mn-chloramphenicol-cefoperazone] systems.

In case of [Mn-oxytetracycline-cefoperazone], 1 : 2, and in case of [Mn-minocycline-cefoperazone], 1 : 1 : 1 complexes were not formed and therefore the values of $\log K_m$ were not calculated for these systems respectively.

The positive values of $\log K_m$ showed that the ternary complexes are more stable than the corresponding binary complexes, whereas, the negative values showed that the ternary complexes are less stable than binary complexes.

The trend in stability constant of complexes was doxycycline < chlortetracycline < oxytetracycline < tetracycline < minocycline < amoxicillin < chloramphenicol. All the tetracyclines including doxycycline and minocycline are of the same structure except in the difference in R_1 and R_2 positions. They all made bond with oxygen of 1, C and oxygen amide (CONH_2) group¹¹ at 2, C atom. The doxycycline formed the complexes of minimum stability, with Mn^{2+} . The lesser stability of chlortetracycline complexes than that of oxytetracycline complexes is due to the presence of more electron withdraw-

Table 1. Stability constants of [Mn-antibiotics-cefoperazone] system

[Mn] = 0.50 mM; μ = 1.0 M NaClO₄; pH = 7.30 ± 0.01; Temp. = 25 °C

Ligands	$\log \beta_{01}$	$\log \beta_{02}$	$\log \beta_{10}$	$\log \beta_{20}$	$\log \beta_{30}$	$\log \beta_{11}$	$\log \beta_{12}$	$\log \beta_{21}$
Doxycycline	-	-	3.21	4.86	7.15	4.10	5.00	7.36
Chlortetracycline	-	-	3.31	5.02	7.78	4.35	5.31	7.88
Oxytetracycline	-	-	4.00	-	8.13	4.85	-	8.40
Tetracycline	-	-	4.12	7.13	8.20	4.93	7.00	8.55
Minocycline	-	-	4.35	7.48	8.56	-	7.16	8.81
Amoxicilline	-	-	4.51	7.93	8.87	5.00	7.50	8.96
Chloramphenicol	-	-	4.67	8.01	9.12	5.12	7.71	9.25
Cefoperazone	1.85	2.73	-	-	-	-	-	-

It is clear from the values of ΔS , ΔG and ΔH of complexes (Table 2) that the complexes are not stable at higher temperature^{9,10}. The negative values of ΔH ensure that the reactions are exothermic in nature.

To compare the stability of binary and ternary complexes, the values of mixing constant $\log K$ was calculated by the following equation⁶,

$$\log K_m = \log \beta_{11} - 1/2 [\log \beta_{02} + \log \beta_{20}]$$

The values of $\log K_m$ were 0.305, 0.475, -0.005, -0.33 and -0.25 respectively for [Mn-doxycycline-cefoperazone], [Mn-chlortetracycline-cefoperazone], [Mn-tetracycline-

ing Cl at R_1 in the former in place of H in the latter¹². In case of tetracycline, H is present both at R_1 and R_2 . Therefore, there is least electronic disturbance in tetracycline in comparison to other tetracycline complexes. The stability of minocycline complexes is lower than that of amoxicillin complexes is owing to the presence of a six membered ring with two double bonds. The complexes with a saturated five membered ring is more stable than a complex with unsaturated six membered ring¹³. The values of stability constants ($\log \beta$) varied from 1.85 to 9.25¹⁴.

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters [Mn-antibiotics-cefoperazone] ternary complexes

Systems	Stability constants				-ΔH (kcal/mol)				-ΔG (kcal/mol)				-ΔS (kcal/mol)			
	log β ₁₁ 25 °C/	log β ₁₂ 25 °C/	log β ₂₁ 25 °C/	log β ₂₂ 25 °C/	log β ₁₁ (35 °C-25 °C) for difference	log β ₁₂ of 10 °C	log β ₂₁	log β ₂₂	log β ₁₁ 25 °C/	log β ₁₂ 25 °C/	log β ₂₁ 25 °C/	log β ₂₂ 25 °C/	log β ₁₁ 25 °C/	log β ₁₂ 25 °C/	log β ₂₁ 25 °C/	log β ₂₂ 25 °C/
	35 °C	35 °C	35 °C	35 °C					35 °C							
[Mn-doxycycline- cefoperazone]	4.10	5.00	7.36	7.00	15.9604	16.8004	15.1204	5.5910	6.8183	10.0365	34.7965	33.4969	33.4972	33.4972	17.0598	17.0602
[Mn-chlortetracycline- cefoperazone]	3.39	4.88	7.88	7.48	40.321	18.0604	16.8004	5.9319	7.2410	10.7456	115.3994	36.3066	36.3070	36.3070	20.3179	20.3184
[Mn-oxytetracycline- cefoperazone]	4.85	-	8.40	8.00	16.8004	-	16.8004	6.6137	-	11.4547	34.1833	-	-	-	17.9384	17.9389
[Mn-tetracycline- cefoperazone]	4.93	7.00	8.55	8.1	18.0604	16.8004	18.9005	6.7284	9.5456	11.6592	38.0455	24.3448	24.3448	24.3448	24.2991	24.2997
[Mn-minocycline- cefoperazone]	-	7.16	8.81	8.4	-	21.0005	17.2204	-	9.7638	12.0138	-	37.7070	37.7070	37.7070	17.4716	17.4722
[Mn-amoxicilline- cefoperazone]	5.00	7.50	8.96	8.56	16.8004	12.6003	16.8004	6.8183	10.2274	12.2183	33.4969	7.9625	7.9630	7.9630	15.3758	15.3764
[Mn-chloramphenicol- cefoperazone]	5.12	7.71	9.25	8.39	9.66023	21.4205	36.1209	6.9819	10.5138	12.6138	8.9875	36.5996	36.5996	36.5996	78.8825	78.8830
[Mn-chloramphenicol- cefoperazone]	4.89	7.2	8.39	8.39	6.89196	10.1476	11.8248	8.9878	8.9878	8.9878	8.9878	8.9878	8.9878	8.9878	8.9878	8.9878

Note

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade and their solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The concentration of Mn^{2+} , antibiotics and cefoperazone were taken in the ratio of 1 : 40 : 40 and current voltage curves were obtained in different pH values. It has been observed that the maximum shift of $E_{1/2}$ was observed within the pH range 7.10–8.50, but pH 7.30 ± 0.01 was selected on account of studying the complexes in human blood pH. Elico-pH Meter (Model LI-120) was used to measure the pH of the analyte at 7.30 ± 0.01 adjusted with dilute solutions of NaOH or $HClO_4$ as required. Potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer was added to stabilize the pH of the analyte. The current voltage curves were recorded on a manual polarograph using polyflex galvanometer (PL-50). The polarographic cell was of Latinin and Lingane¹⁵ type in which capillary of 5.0 cm in length with 0.04 mM in diameters was used. The $m^{2/3}t^{1/6}$ value was $2.40 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{1/2}$ at 60.02 cm effective height of mercury. The resistance of the cell was less than 250 Ω therefore; IR correction was not made.

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References

1. T. Korzybski, Z. Kowszyk-Gindifer and W. Kuryloicz, "Antibiotics Origin, Nature and Properties", Pwn Polish Sci-

- entific Publishers, Warszawa, 1967, 1.
2. A. K. Kesharwsani and F. Khan, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 2002, **18**, 413.
3. M. Riaz and N. Pilpel, *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1984, **36**, 153.
4. F. Khan and L. Tantuvay, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal. (Netherland)*, 2002, **27**, 933.
5. P. J. Gellings, *Z. Electrochem. Ber. Bunsenges Phys Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 481; 1963, **67**, 167.
6. W. B. Schaap and D. L. McMaster, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4699.
7. R. Tamamushi and N. Tanaka, *Z. Phys. Chem., Neue Folge*, 1963, **39**, 117.
8. R. Tamamushi, K. Ishibashi and N. Tanaka, *Z. Phys. Chem., Neue Folge*, 1962, **35**, 211.
9. F. Khan and A. V. Mahajani, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 165.
10. A. Zaddi and F. Khan, *J. Inst. Chem. (India)*, 2000, **72**, 104.
11. F. Khan and F. Khan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **83**, 591.
12. L. Tantuvay and F. Khan, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 2004, **20**, 327.
13. A. E. Martel and M. Calvin, "Chemistry of Metal Chelates Compounds", 2nd ed., 1963, **61**, 134
14. M. D. Walker and D. L. Williams, *J. Chem. Soc. (Dalton)*, 1974, 1186.
15. L. Meites, "Polarographic Technique", 2nd ed., Interscience Publishers, New York, 1965, 1-62.